

A. Artifact Appendix

A.1 Abstract

This artifact is a Docker image that contains all the requirements and scripts to replicate the experiments of the sections 5.3 and 5.4 of the paper. The image includes the implementation of scalar interpolation algorithm, the PolyBench benchmark suite, and the scripts to run the benchmarks using auto-tuner and the cost model.

A.2 Artifact check-list (meta-information)

- **Algorithm:** A loop transformation to add scalar instructions into the vectorized code.
- **Program:** PolyBenchC-4.2.1 benchmark.
- **Compilation:** Includes LLVM 17.0.0.
- **Run-time environment:** Tested on Ubuntu 22.04 (6.8.0-48-generic) with Docker version 27.3.1.
- **Hardware:** Tested on Intel Xeon E5-2698 v4 CPUs.
- **Metrics:** Execution time.
- **Output:** Execution times in form of CSV files and the corresponding graphs for each experiment.
- **Experiments:** Cost model effectiveness (Section 5.3) and Scalar Interpolation performance (Section 5.4)
- **How much disk space required (approximately)?:** 1.9 GB for the docker image.
- **How much time is needed to complete experiments (approximately)?:** About 8 hours for a single run. It takes about 80 hours to run the experiments 10 times and replicate the paper experiments
- **Publicly available?:** Yes.
- **Code licenses (if publicly available)?:** Ohio State University Software Distribution License, Apache License v2.0 with LLVM Exceptions.
- **Archived (provide DOI)?:** 10.5281/zenodo.14090974

A.3 Description

A.3.1 How to access

The artifact is archived: 10.5281/zenodo.14061541.

A.3.2 Hardware dependencies

An Intel Xeon E5-2698 v4 CPU, because the cost model for the algorithm depends on specific hardware characteristics. The transformation still performs on other architectures, however the results may differ from the paper.

A.3.3 Software dependencies

A working Docker installation.

A.4 Installation

A.4.1 CPU Frequency Scaling

To have consistent results, we need to lock the CPU frequency. In the experiments shown in the paper, it was locked at 2.2 GHz.

```
$ sudo cpupower frequency-set -g performance
$ sudo cpupower frequency-set -u 2.2GHz
$ sudo cpupower frequency-set -d 2.2GHz
```

A.4.2 Docker Setup

After downloading the compressed docker image file, load the image via the following command, and run the container:

```
$ docker load --input scalar-interpolation.tar.gz
$ docker run -it si:v1
```

A.5 Experiment workflow

After running the container, you can set up the `config.json` file to change the experiment setting. The parameters of this file are explained in more detail in A.7.

```
$ nano config.json
```

The following commands run the experiments and generate the results.

```
$ python3 main.py
$ python3 main.py -a
```

The first command runs the experiments whose results are shown in Figures 2 and 3 of the paper, and the second command runs the experiment whose results are illustrated in Figure 5. The results of these experiments are stored in the *figures* and *tables* folders, to retrieve them, one should run the following commands:

```
$ ID=$(docker ps -q --filter 'ancestor=si:v1')
$ docker cp $ID:/home/si/figures/ .
$ docker cp $ID:/home/si/tables/ .
```

A.6 Evaluation and expected results

Using a similar environment and setup, the results should follow the same trend as shown in the paper. Yet, changing different factors, such as using a different CPU, or changing the number of repetitions may affect the final results.

A.7 Experiment customization

After running the container, the experiment scripts can be set up using the `config.json` file. This file contains some file paths required to run the scripts and some parameters that can change the experiments, including:

- **repeat:** If it is set to N ($N > 1$), the experiments will be repeated N times and the scripts report average execution time.
- **si_factors:** list of candidate SIFs for the auto-tuner.
- **results_file:** a path to a file to save execution time and standard deviation results for the experiments.
- **measurement_retrials:** If it is set to N , it retries each measurement up to N times when the measurement fails for any reason.

A.8 Notes

- On the Experiment Workflow instructions, after running each command, the average execution time of each benchmark and the standard deviation are stored in a file whose path is set by **results_file** in `config.json`. This file must be removed before running each experiment replication command because it also serves as a caching mechanism in cases where the running experiment crashes.
- You may need sudo privileges when running docker depending on the host's configuration.